

DURABILITY OF FLAX-BASALT HYBRID COMPOSITES FOR MARINE APPLICATIONS

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Keywords: Hybrid composites, Basalt fibres, Flax fibres, Durability, Salt spray environment test

ABSTRACT

The aim of the present work is to evaluate the influence of external layers of mat basalt on the durability behaviour and performances of flax/epoxy laminates. To this scope, long-term aging tests were performed to evaluate the durability of the two different laminates in critical environmental conditions.

In particular, Flax composites were constituted by ten layers of bidirectional flax fabric whereas hybrid laminates (i.e. Flax-Basalt) were produced by replacing four external layers of bidirectional flax with four layers of basalt mat. Both laminates had a total average thickness equal to 3 mm.

The samples were exposed to critical environmental conditions following the ASTM B 117 standard. The salt fog had a chemical composition of 5% NaCl solution (pH between 6.5 and 7.2). In the climatic chamber, the samples were aged continuously with a temperature of 35°C.

Every 2 weeks some samples were mechanically tested until a whole period of 2 months. The removed samples, washed and dried, were preserved in a sealed plastic storage bag with silica gel desiccant to ensure no further corrosion evolution during storage. Three point bending tests, dynamic mechanical tests (DMTA) and Charpy impact tests were performed according to ASTM D 790, ASTM D 4065 and ISO 179 standards, respectively.

Moreover, five samples of both laminates were removed periodically, dried with a lint free cloth, and weighed with the aim to evaluate the water absorption.

The experimental results showed that aging resistance of Flax composites can be improved by using basalt layers as outer laminae thus evidencing that hybridization with basalt fibres is a practical approach for enhancing mechanical properties and durability of natural fibre composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

The physical and mechanical properties of fibre reinforced polymer composites (FRP), e.g. the glass transition temperature, the elastic modulus, the failure stress, the ductility and the impact strength vary as a function of time, temperature and ambient conditions. Severe environmental conditions influence the strength of both the matrix of the polymeric composite and the fibre-matrix adhesion leading to an overall decrement of performances of the composites.

For this reason, design engineers need to know safe and economic values of the characteristics of those materials to adequately dimension the structures for their life-cycle [1].

To this aim, a comparison between experimental results obtained in laboratory and after actual exposure has been made [1-4], but there is still great uncertainty on the long-term evolution of material performances. Hence, the knowledge of the FRPs behaviour under aggressive environmental conditions has not a solution free of problems since the action of moisture in fibres may induce damage and the effect of moisture and temperature may reduce their expected durability.

In the last few years, the use of natural fibres as reinforcement of composite materials, as an alternative to the synthetics has received growing attention, owing to their specific properties, price, advantages for health, and recyclability.

In particular, flax fibre is an inexpensive and easily available bast fibre, widely used as reinforcement in polymer matrix composites. Nevertheless, being a lignocellulosic material, flax fibre also possesses some drawbacks (e.g. hydrophilic nature, low mechanical properties, and poor adhesion with several different polymeric matrices). In particular, due to its susceptibility to moisture absorption, its aging resistance in humid environments is limited and its application is restricted to non-structural interior products. Dhakal *et al.* [5] compared the effects of water immersion aging on the mechanical properties of flax and jute fibre reinforced composites. They showed that the percentage of moisture uptake and diffusion coefficient was higher for jute-reinforced specimens compared with flax. The mechanical characterization showed a higher susceptibility to water immersion of jute composites rather than flax ones. In particular, flax samples lost almost 40% of strength and 69% of modulus after immersion in a de-ionised water bath at 25°C for a period of 961 hours whereas the jute wet samples lost 60% of strength and 80% of modulus, respectively.

Hybridization of flax fibres with stronger and more corrosion-resistant fibres can also improve the stiffness, strength, as well as moisture resistant behaviour of the composite. Using a hybrid composite containing two or more types of different fibres, the advantages of one type of fibre could complement what are lacking in the other [6]. Hybrid composites containing flax fibres have been widely studied in the last decade [7-12]. Nevertheless, at the best of our knowledge, very few studies concern the hybridization of flax fibres with mineral fibres as basalt ones [13-14].

Due to their good properties such as chemical stability, non-toxicity, non-combustible, resistant to high temperatures, thermal and acoustic insulation besides to mechanical properties better than those of E-glass ones, basalt fibres began to be used as a brand new reinforcing material for hybrid composite laminates [15]. Moreover, basalt-based materials can be considered environmentally friendly and non-hazardous even if the current production technology for continuous basalt fibres is very similar to that used for E-glass manufacturing. The main difference is that E-glass is made from a complex batch of materials whereas basalt filament is made from melting basalt rock with no other additives and, as a consequence, with an advantage in terms of cost.

Aim of the present work is to evaluate the influence of external basalt layers on the durability of flax/epoxy laminates in salt spray aging environment.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

All the laminates investigated were realized with a single lamination using the vacuum bagging technique, cured at room temperature for 24 hours and then post-cured at 50 °C for 8 hours.

In particular, flax laminates were constituted by ten layers of bidirectional flax fabric in a matrix of epoxy resin (i.e. SP 106 by Gurit) mixed with own hardener. This kind of flax fabric is an unbalanced plain weave fabric with areal weight equal to 150 g/m² and cost per unit of area of 6 €/m². The hybrid composites were produced by replacing four external layers of bidirectional flax with four layers of basalt mat (randomly oriented fibres, with areal weight of 100 g/m² and cost per unit of area of 9 €/m²).

With the aim of evaluate the influence of external layer of mat basalt on the durability behaviour and performances of flax/epoxy laminates, both the laminates were exposed to critical environmental conditions following the ASTM B 117 standard. The salt fog had a chemical composition of 5% NaCl solution (pH between 6.5 and 7.2). In the climatic chamber, the samples were aged continuously with a temperature of 35°C.

During the environmental aging process, five samples were taken out every 2 weeks and mechanically tested (i.e. by means of quasi-static three point bending, dynamic-mechanical and impact tests) until a whole period of 2 months. The removed samples, washed and dried, were preserved in a sealed plastic storage bag with silica gel desiccant to ensure no further corrosion evolution during storage.

Three point bending tests were performed according to ASTM D790 standard, using a Zwick/Roell Universal Testing Machine (UTM) equipped with a load cell of 5 kN. Five prismatic samples (3 mm x

13 mm x 115 mm) of both laminates for each aging condition were tested (i.e. non-aged, 15 days, 30 days, 45 days and 60 days aged samples) setting the span length equal to 96 mm and the crosshead speed to 5.12 mm/min.

Dynamic mechanical analysis was carried out using a Metravib dynamic mechanical analyzers model DMA+150, equipped with a load cell of 150 N. The experiments were performed under the tensile mode at frequency of 1 Hz. Five prismatic samples (16 mm x 4 mm x 1 mm) of both laminates for each aging condition were tested. The tests were conducted at temperatures from room to 150 °C with heating rate of 5°C/min, under nitrogen atmosphere.

Impact tests was carried out according to EN ISO 179 standard, using a CEAST Charpy pendulum model 9050, equipped with a pendulum of potential energy equal to 25 J and impact speed of 3.8 m/s. Five un-notched prismatic samples (80 mm x 10 mm x 3 mm) of both laminates for each aging condition were tested.

Five samples of both laminates were periodically removed from the climatic chamber within the range 48 h-1440 h, dried with a lint free cloth, and weighed to analyse the weight change of the composites. The absorption of the composites in weight percentage W was determined by the weight gain relative to the oven dry weight:

$$W = 100 (P_T - P_0) / P_0 \quad (1)$$

where P_T is the wet weight at time t and P_0 is the dry weight of the sample.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Water Uptake

The water uptake percentage of Flax and Flax-Basalt laminates vs. aging time are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Water absorption of flax and flax-basalt composites.

It is worth noting that Flax and Flax-Basalt laminates both followed Fick's law since water absorption quickly increased and reached a plateau after ~700 h. The maximum water absorbed value was of about 9% and 23% for Flax-Basalt and Flax laminates, respectively. The percentage of water uptake with time is far greater in the case of Flax laminates than the Flax-Basalt ones. Both types of composite specimens showed saturation due to water uptake but flax-basalt specimens stabilized at much lower values of moisture uptake.

Since the saturated levels of moisture uptake is one of the most important property degradations in

the materials exposed to critical environmental conditions, hybrid laminates proved superior to flax ones. As the sample expands and shrinks, debonding between the matrix and fibres occurs creating voids, which act as a reservoir for moisture thereby increasing its overall saturation level.

The significant difference in the weight gain between Hybrid and Flax laminates is attributed to the hydrophilic properties of lignocellulosic flax fibres. Flax fibre contains cellulose and hemicellulose compositions up to 71-75% and 18.6-20.6%, respectively. These compositions contain numerous hydroxyl groups and carboxyl groups, which would interact with water molecules via hydrogen bonding [16]. The numerous hydroxyl groups in the cellulose and hemicellulose lead to poor interface and poor resistance of the fibres to the moisture absorption, which promote the water gain of the Flax composites.

Consequently, the external hydrophobic basalt layers in Hybrid laminates preserve the internal lignocellulosic layers from the degradation phenomena due to the aging environmental exposition.

The different trends also suggested that basalt fibre appreciably influences water diffusion into the polymeric network due to improved fibre/matrix interfacial bond: i.e. the stronger interfacial adhesion concerning Flax-Basalt laminates reduces water accumulation in the interfacial voids, prevents water from entering the flax fibres thus leading to lesser water-absorption rate due to aging exposure.

These results are in accordance with the literature [17]: i.e. compared with mineral fibres reinforced polymer composites, the weight gain of flax fabrics reinforced composites are more significant.

3.2 Three point bending tests

Figure 2 shows the stress vs. strain (Figure 2a) and modulus vs. strain curves (Figure 2b) for non-aged Flax and Flax-Basalt laminates.

Figure 2: Stress-strain and modulus-strain curves for (a) Flax and (b) Flax-Basalt non-aged composites.

It is possible to identify three different zones:

- **Linear zone:** In the first part of the curve, the relation between stress and strain can be considered linear and the modulus is constant. In this zone, the behavior can be treated as pure linear elastic. In the case of Flax composites, this zone is limited to very small strain values (up to 0.3% and 3000 MPa modulus). If Flax-Basalt composites are considered, this zone is much wider (up to 2% in strain corresponding to 4000 MPa in Modulus).
- **Non-linear zone:** for higher deformations, the relation between stress and strain turn into a non-linear relation and the stiffness decrease. This effect is due to an increment in deformation at the interface between the lamina, which results in an increment of shear stresses. In the case of Flax composite, such behavior happens at small load values due to poor interlaminar strength. For Flax-Basalt composites, for strain values higher than 2%, a drop in modulus is highlighted and the plastic behavior due to the shear deformation of the resin gradually emerges. However, for Flax composites, the plastic contribution becomes preponderant and local delamination and micro-debonding phenomena occur and they lead to increments in strain with small load variations. This region is characterized by a plateau

in the stress-strain curve and an asymptotic decrease for the modulus-strain curve.

- Plateau zone: for Flax composites, a progressive yielding behavior is highlighted. Otherwise, for Flax-Basalt composites show an instantaneous collapse corresponding to about 3.5% in strain.

Figure 3 shows the variations of flexural modulus and strength varying the aging time. It is possible to note that the mechanical properties of Flax-Basalt composites are higher than Flax ones, for each aging condition. The enhancements in mechanical properties of hybrid composite over Flax one is expected since weaker and less stiff flax fibres is replaced by stronger and stiffer basalt fibres.

Moreover, the Flax composites experience greater decrements of both mechanical properties. Compared to control samples (i.e. non-aged samples), the reduction of the flexural modulus of the 60 days-aged samples is about 16% and 56% for Flax-Basalt and Flax composites, respectively. As concern the flexural strength, Flax-Basalt composites experience a variation of 10% whereas Flax ones of 48%. Moreover, it is worth to note that the degradation in the flexural modulus is more serious than that of the strength

Figure 3: (a) Flexural modulus and (b) strength for Flax and Flax-Basalt composites.

The high reduction in flexural properties of Flax composites can be attributed to the degradation of flax fibres, the epoxy matrix and the fibre/matrix interfaces during the aging exposition. Voids and cracks within the thermoset matrix allows penetration of moisture to the flax fibres. As discussed above, flax fibres consist mainly of cellulose and hemicellulose: i.e. hemicellulose with open structure containing numerous hydroxyl and acetyl groups, which is responsible for moisture absorption and for the thermal degradation of flax fibre [18] and cellulose, determining the fibre mechanical properties, is embedded in hemicellulose matrices. Thus, the failure of cellulose and hemicellulose during aging exposition leads to a weakness of fibre-matrix adhesion. Furthermore, the water molecules can remove the hydrophobic substances of the fibre (e.g. hydrocarbons, waxes and lignin) thus further degrading the fibre/matrix interfacial bonding [19]. As clearly known, a weak fibre/matrix adhesion leads to low mechanical properties of the composites.

Moreover, both chemical and physical degradation of the epoxy matrix can occur due to the aging exposition. As concerns the chemical degradation, NaCl exists in the salt fog as cations and anions, which would penetrate together with the water molecules into the composite, damaging the matrix, fibre and the fibre/matrix interface. The swelling degradation (i.e. physical degradation) of flax fibres can degrade their tensile properties, which, in turn, decrease the flexural properties of the composites. Swelling by penetration of moisture causes micro-cracking in the epoxy matrix and interfacial debonding at the interface. However, the effect of water on the properties of the matrix is only secondary. Therefore, the major sources of degradation during aging come from the flax fibres and the fibre/matrix interface.

Consequently, lower degradation in flexural properties of Hybrid laminates can be attributed to the presence of mineral fibres (e.g. basalt) in the external layers, which screen the internal layers from the above degradation phenomena.

3.3 Dynamic mechanical analysis

Three important parameters that can be determined from dynamic mechanical analysis are:

- storage modulus, which is a measure of the maximum energy stored in the material during one cycle of oscillation and which gives an indication of the stiffness behaviour of the sample;
- loss modulus, which is directly proportional to the amount of energy that has been dissipated as heat by the sample;
- a mechanical damping term, $\tan \delta$, which is the ratio of the loss modulus to the storage modulus and is related to the degree of molecular mobility in the material [20].

During measurement of the storage and loss modulus and damping property of a composite over a wide range of temperatures, glass transition temperature (T_g) can be detected. The T_g is a reversible change of the polymer composite between rubbery and glassy states. The T_g can be detected as a sudden and considerable change in the storage modulus and a peak in the tangent delta curve.

Figure 4: (a) Glass transition temperature and (b) height of damping for Flax and Flax-Basalt composites.

The amplitude of the $\tan \delta$ peaks depends from the magnitude of dissipative phenomena. Hence, its value is strictly related both to the mobility of the polymeric chain and to the fibre-matrix adhesion: i.e. a weak fibre-matrix adhesion leads to higher values of $\tan \delta$ [21] while a good fibre-matrix adhesion limits the mobility of the polymer chains thus reducing the damping.

From Figure 4 it is possible to note that both laminates experience a decrement in T_g values and an increment in the peak height of damping, at increasing the aging time. This means the exposition to critical environmental conditions leads to an increment of the internal mobility (i.e. polymer chains mobility and weakness of the adhesion between fibres and matrix).

Moreover, Flax composites experience greater decrements of glass transition temperature than hybrid composites, due to the weak fibre/matrix interfacial adhesion. In particular, by comparing the non-aged samples and those aged for 60 days, the decrements of T_g are equal 9.9 °C (from 92.8 °C to 82.9°C) and 21.3 °C (from 120.9 °C to 99.6 °C) for Flax-Basalt and Flax composites, respectively.

3.4 Impact tests

The impact test revealed a very different behavior between Flax and Flax-Basalt composites. In particular, the impact strength of non-aged Flax-Basalt samples is 28% higher than flax ones due to presence of the external basalt layers in the hybrid structures. It is possible to assert that Flax-Basalt composites do not show significant variation of impact strength whereas Flax composites increase its energy absorption capability with increasing the aging time.

Two different degradation mechanisms contribute to the modification of the impact properties of polymer composites exposed to critical aging condition:

- The water absorption lead to plasticization of the resin and a decreasing in maximum stress.

- The increasing of the maximum deformation is related to the ability to absorb energy restraining the effects of the aging on the impact strength properties.

Considering Flax composites, the increment in plastic deformation is predominant on the effect of the maximum stress reduction and this is related to a higher amount of absorbed water (i.e. 23% wt.). Therefore, the increment in impact strength of Flax composites can be attributed to the increase of plastic behavior induced by the aging process.

Figure 5: Impact strength for Flax and Flax-Basalt composites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The influence of external layers of mat basalt on durability behaviour and performances of Flax laminates was evaluated in this paper. To this scope, long-term aging tests were performed following the ASTM B 117 standard.

In particular, five samples were mechanically tested (three point bending tests, dynamic mechanical tests and Charpy impact tests) every 2 weeks until a whole period of 2 months. Moreover, five samples of both laminates were periodically removed from the climatic chamber and weighted to evaluate their mass gain.

From the experimental results it is possible to state that:

- the percentage of water uptake with aging time is far greater in the case of Flax laminates than Flax-Basalt ones. Both types of composites showed saturation but Flax-Basalt specimens stabilized at much lower values of moisture uptake;
- the quasi-static flexural properties of Flax-Basalt composites are higher than those of Flax ones, for each aging condition. Moreover, Flax composites show greater decrements of both modulus and strength. In particular, by comparing the non-aged samples and those aged for 60 days, the decrements of the flexural modulus are about 16% and 56% for Flax-Basalt and Flax composites, respectively. As concern the flexural strength, Flax composites experience a variation of 48% whereas Flax-Basalt ones of 10%;
- both laminates experience a decrement in T_g values and an increment in the peak height of damping, at increasing the aging time. Moreover, Flax composites show greater decrements of T_g . In particular, by comparing the non-aged samples and those aged for 60 days, the decrements of T_g are equal 9.9 °C (from 92.8°C to 82.9°C) and 21.3°C (from 120.9°C to 99.6°C) for Flax-Basalt and Flax composites, respectively;
- Flax-Basalt composites do not show significant variation of impact strength whereas Flax composites increase its energy absorption capability by increasing the aging time.

The present paper highlights that aging resistance of flax reinforced composites can be improved by using basalt layers as outer laminae. This improvement can be attributed both to slower degradation under the aging exposition and to better fibre/epoxy matrix adhesion evidenced by basalt fibre, rather than flax one.

In conclusion, it is demonstrated that hybridization with basalt fibres is a practical approach for enhancing mechanical properties and durability of natural fibre composites.

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